

**THE MECHANISM OF IMPROVEMENT OF PROFESSIONAL READERS,
HELPING THEM TO PROVIDE SCHOOL AND ADULT EDUCATION
INTEGRATION.**

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Abstract: in school and in adult education this article reader-directed to the coverage of the pedagogical basis of motivation given to the young professional. Also in the article the reader-young people in the profession right at problems, ways to eliminate them think concerning the gaps in practice.

Keywords: continuing education, professional referral, specialized training, technological education, continuous system.

The article middle school students with specialized education in the school within the framework of the implementation of the professional work of the organization based on a study of methods of directing. Literary analysis the activities of qualified specialists in this field, their specialized education of the content, functions, features and pedagogical complex business entities according to a systematic phenomenon can be called. The study pedagogical theory and practice the problems clearly, to understand its purpose and content to achieve in need of theoretical and empirical studies directed at actively summarize the basic recipe and is currently in phase will determine that (1). the pedagogical process, which established a system of continuing education institutions in the implementation of the ongoing news of the effectiveness of education on the basis of the recipient of the received knowledge, modern technology and information and communication technologies able to spend learning, intellectual formation and the teacher the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as the level of development determines the growth of pedagogical skills and professional abilities. (2)

The body of knowledge of certain interest to the reader is the basis for the formation of stable professional. Also, the methods and analysis this analysis in the form of professional directing the work in the first place, future of the upper and aims to prepare students in grades independent profession to make an informed choice. The school students' self-preparation and process to ensure the professional character of different forms in the method, professional occupations and the world of work while directing readers are starting to get acquainted with the basics of modern production. The direct result of professional work in the interest of the professional development of governors of the latest educational secondary school,. In addition to the lessons from the school should become a specific tool, two systems and the integration of additional content in the overall process should be closely related with its educational sciences general education within the areas of science and to be studied them; they constitute a permanent part of the basic curriculum. On the other hand, the variability of the process of education and its main task to provide (3). "Extracurricular lessons" to be a mandatory component of the school's basic educational program, educational activities organized in various forms, they are special readers. The process of integration of all three components: general education, adult education classes for children between special and meaningful to establish additional associated need to pay attention. The science that means students will show their abilities depth study of particular interest. Make a difference and that that creates radical in addition to school sports, art, additional courses on professional readers the opportunity to create his own destiny set (4). If so,

the integration of two functions available to each component in the system is a set of variability in this process, personalize, constructive activity and the person is there to rely on the formation of the professional preparation of students before the implementation of the preparation, referral program of additional education for children with specific style [5]. On the other hand, focus on learning to continuously improve quality associated with new technologies, methods, forms, research and development, teaching, methods of assessment of learners' achievements, the general characteristic will make the process of additional education for children [1, p. 6]. In addition to these human activities, linking the school with the school becomes between components.

As a conclusion we can say that-based education relies on the following main principles: continuity, conformity natural, cultural compatibility, openness. Additional education for children these principles, continuing education is characterized by the constant search to focus. Technologies, methods of work, the form, as well as improvement of the methods and criteria of assessment of student achievement, in the field of education continues to seek new forms of organization, but this is not enough to update the system to get additional education of children with great freedom and here's the source, openness, the initial focus of the personal development of students and the improvement of mechanisms to ensure the integration of the two systems should be [2, p. 7]

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